

TEX-KR project - Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action – European Union Project (Grant agreement no. 101025131)

List of archives and museums visited and accessed on site and remotely

- United States

Yale University Art Gallery

1111 Chapel Street (at York Street)

New Haven, CT, USA

<https://artgallery.yale.edu/>

Collection of Cambodian silk textiles, gift of Helen Ibbitson Jessup donated in 2017.

Source:

“Acquisitions July 1, 2017–June 30, 2018,”

<https://artgallery.yale.edu/sites/default/files/files/bulletin/Pub-Bull-acquisitions-2018.pdf>

> Visited in March 2022

Yale Genocide Database

Genocide Studies Program | POB 208206 | New Haven, CT, 06520-8206 USA

<https://gsp.yale.edu/cambodian-genocide-databases-cgdb>

Database based on the records from the Tuol Sleng Genocide Database

> Accessed remotely

- France

Bibliothèque universitaire des langues et civilisations (BULAC)

65 Rue des Grands Moulins, 75013 Paris, FR

<https://www.bulac.fr/>

Archival collection of periodicals and propaganda files such as:

Revue Kambuja (Issue 54, September 1969)

Images de la République Khmère, protectorat des United States of America du Front uni national du Kampuchea (1972)

Images de la lutte armée et de la vie du peuple khmer en zones libérées (1972)

> Visited in June 2022

Bibliothèque de l'École Française d'Extrême-Orient (EFEO)

22, av du Président Wilson 75116 Paris, FR

<https://www.efeo.fr/base.php?code=72>

Archives about the National Museum of Cambodia's management and collections during the French protectorate

> Visited in June 2022 and July 2023

Photographic database

<https://collection.efeo.fr/ws/web/app/report/les-fonds.html>

> Accessed remotely

Musée du quai Branly – Jacques Chirac

37 Quai Jacques Chirac, 75007 Paris, FR

<https://www.quaibrantly.fr/en/>

Large collection of Cambodian textiles
Large collection of photographs about Cambodia (1900s-1950s)

> Visited in May 2024

- Cambodia

National Museum of Cambodia

Preah Ang Eng St. (13), Phnom Penh 120211, Cambodia

https://www.cambodiamuseum.info/en_collection.html

Collection of Cambodian textiles acquired pre-1975

> Visited in May and November 2022

Library at the National Museum of Cambodia

Preah Ang Eng St. (13), Phnom Penh 120211, Cambodia

https://cambodiamuseum.info/en_projects_activities/research%20library.html#:~:text=Museum%20Library,of%20the%20Main%20Gallery%20entrance.

Archival records (inventory, catalogues, index cards) dating from the French protectorate about the textile collection acquired pre-1975 by French museum directors.

> Visited in May 2022

Tuol Sleng Genocide Museum

Street 113

Phnom Penh 12304, Cambodia

<https://tuolsleng.gov.kh/en/>

Collection of textiles and clothing recovered from S-21 torture centre

Digitized database containing prisoners' records, photographic prints and forced confessions

> Visited in November 2022

National Archives of Cambodia

Street 61, Hing Pen Street

Sangkat Wat Phnom, Khan Daun Penh

Phnom Penh, Cambodia

<https://nac.gov.kh/>

Archival records from Democratic Kampuchea (1975-79) about textile production

> Visited in November 2022

Documentation Centre of Cambodia (DC-CAM) online repository

Mansion 11 Street 256

Phnom Penh 120207

Cambodia

<https://databases.dccam.org/>

Database stemming from Tuol Sleng Genocide Museum records

Photographs from the period 1960s-70s

> Remote consultation in 2022-23

- Australia

National Library of Australia

Parkes Pl W, Canberra ACT 2600

<https://www.nla.gov.au/>

Accessing Neil Manton's archives. This material was assembled while Manton worked as a diplomat and consultant specialising in the arts and cultures of Southeast Asia.

<https://catalogue.nla.gov.au/catalog/836568>

> Remote consultation in 2022

- Switzerland

ICRC Archives

International Committee of the Red Cross

Library and Public archives

19, avenue de la Paix - 1202 Geneva – Switzerland

<https://avarchives.icrc.org/>

Photographs of the International Red Cross missions in Cambodia from 1970 to 1980.

> Remote consultation in 2022-23